

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PREPARATION OF GEORGIA'S INDEPENDENCE BASED ON INTERNATIONAL TREATIES AND THE FIRST YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

The presented article concerns the historical struggle of Georgia against the Russian Empire and the Soviet Union. The first occupation of Georgia took place back in the 19th century, when Russia occupied the regions of Georgia and annexed it to the empire. However, the struggle of the Georgian people bore fruit and gained independence in 1918. Unfortunately, this independence turned out to be short-lived. In 1921, Georgia was again Sovietized.

The Georgian people did not stop fighting for independence. They made great sacrifices so that Georgia would remain an independent political entity on the world map. In the process of this struggle, many Georgians took to the stage of action and played a major role in the success of this struggle. Among them, the role of the first dissident president of Georgia, Zviad Gamsakhurdia, is particularly noteworthy. He entered this struggle fully aware and prepared. He understood the complexity of this struggle well and did his utmost to ensure that Georgia successfully completed this struggle, appreciated the sacrifice of its heroic ancestors, and made the dreams of thousands of partisans come true.

Despite the difficulties, the work of the first president of Georgia and his team in the history of Georgia is invaluable.

Keywords: Georgia, International Agreements, Zviad Gamsakhurdia, Independence, National Movement.

Research methods: In order to obtain the results of the research of the problematic posed in the article, we used empirical materials. Relying on them, studying and properly analyzing them allowed us to assess the main goal of the foreign policy of the government of Zviad Gamsakhurdia, which was expressed precisely in the international recognition of Georgia. We also used the comparative, historical, logical analysis, structural-functional, formal legal methods. This allowed us to make an objective political and legal assessment of the foreign policy course of the Georgian state in 1990-1992.

Historical precedents

=The Georgian statehood, which dates back centuries and spans three thousand years of history, was lost by the Georgian nation in the 19th century as a result of the annexation by the Russian Empire. The Georgian population never came to terms with the loss of freedom and fought to restore its independence. The Act of Independence of May 26, 1918, declared the restoration of the abolished statehood and by virtue of this document, the Democratic Republic of Georgia was proclaimed. According to the results of multi-party elections, the independent state had an elected government and representative bodies. Work began on a draft constitution, which was approved by the parliament in 1921.

Shortly after the declaration of independence, three years later, Soviet Russia occupied Georgia again. It is interesting that this fact was preceded by the conclusion of the 1920 treaty, by virtue of which Soviet Russia recognized Georgia as an independent political entity and concluded a cooperation agreement with it. In the future, this treaty will play a very important role in gaining independence and international recognition.

The existence of this treaty is enough to note the fact that Georgia did not voluntarily join the Soviet Union. The democratically elected government did not sign the capitulation, but simply left the country and went into exile. The Georgian government continued to work on the Georgian cause in Europe, in particular in France.

During the period of its existence as one of the allied republics within the Soviet Union, the great figures of Georgia did not stop fighting for the restoration of independence, despite repression and persecution. These repressions claimed the lives of thousands of educated and party-minded people.

The use of international treaties in the struggle for independence

The Soviet Union was, by its very nature, a completely undemocratic, totalitarian-type state. However, despite this, it tried to have a democratic image in the international arena, and therefore it signed international treaties by virtue of which, together with other states, it recognized human rights, their freedom, the right to vote and other fundamental rights. Two main agreements should be distinguished from these treaties:

One of the first treaties is the Helsinki Declaration of 1975 (August 1), which recognized: sovereign equality, respect for the rights inherent in sovereignty; refraining from the threat or use of force; inviolability of borders; territorial integrity of states; peaceful settlement of disputes; non-interference in internal affairs; respect for human rights, including freedom of speech, conscience, religion and movement; equal rights and self-determination of peoples; cooperation between

states; and the faithful fulfillment of obligations under international law¹³.

The second agreement that the Soviet Union signed was the Geneva Conventions of 1949¹⁴. This convention also recognized human rights and called on its signatories to protect them.

Both of these treaties were used by Zviad Gamsakhurdia, a fighter for Georgian independence, and his friends against the Soviet Union, and the national movement, relying on this concept, tried to protect itself from Soviet aggression.

In the 1970s, the ground was so prepared for the beginning of a new stage of the national movement that a new group of dissidents decided to establish the "Helsinki Group". This group monitored Soviet human rights violations, distributed banned literature, and tried to awaken and unite society in a united fight to restore the country's independence. This group had extensive international connections, recognition, and support in Europe. The Soviet government did not suppress their activities and soon arrested members of this group. Fortunately, their power was no longer as weak as, for example, in the 30s and 40s, and dissidents escaped execution. After the liberation, cultural and political agitation for the restoration of Georgia's independence and separation from the Soviet Union began in full force. In this struggle, Zviad Gamsakhurdia, Merab Kostava and others very well understood international law and called on Moscow to respect its norms. It was precisely by virtue of these concepts that they had the right to demand national self-determination. The movement of this group was so popular and supported by the Georgian population that gradually rallies began to be organized, more and more people joined this struggle, more people became aware of the real past history of the country, and the national spirit was increasingly awakening. Zviad Gamsakhurdia was the locomotive of these processes. He was distinguished by great education, enthusiasm, honesty and selfless love for his homeland. His speeches did not go unnoticed, and thanks to his charisma, the national liberation movement, fully supported by the Georgian people, soon decided to take the appropriate steps to prepare for the declaration of independence. This was a very difficult process and required great caution and effort. The continuous protests on Rustaveli Avenue were violently dispersed several times, but the most violent crackdown occurred on April 9, 1989, when Soviet troops brutally dispersed peaceful protesters. This fact received a great response both within the country and in the international arena.

The Difficulties of Independence

The tragedy of April 9 further strengthened the desire for independence and strengthened the belief that nothing was impossible. This fact forced the already weakened Soviet government to surrender to Georgia and agree to hold multi-party elections. The unrest was preceded by a referendum. The political and ideological

significance of the referendum is very great in the recent history of Georgia. On March 31, 1991, a referendum was held in Georgia. The referendum question was: "Do you agree or not to restore the state independence of Georgia on the basis of the Act of Independence of May 26, 1918?" 3.3 million people gave a positive answer. This means that 99.08% of citizens who went to the ballot boxes supported the restoration of Georgia's independence. It was precisely on this basis that the Act of Restoration of Independence was adopted on April 9, 1991. About a century later, independence was finally declared, which the Georgian people and their leaders achieved through great struggle and sacrifice.

Before the October 1990 elections, the political coalition "Round Table - Free Georgia" was formed, which received a large majority of votes (81 seats) in the first multi-party elections. A total of 10 political entities participated in these elections, including the "Communist Party". The new parliament elected the first number on the winning coalition's list - Zviad Gamsakhurdia - as the head of the government.

The restoration of the state independence of the Republic of Georgia was fully consistent with the Charter of the United Nations, the Helsinki and Vienna Acts. These agreements recognize the right of the people to independently determine the political destiny of their country. And especially if it has three thousand years of experience of living as an independent political entity. This is exactly what we meant above when we noted that Zviad Gamsakhurdia used international agreements well against the Soviet government.

Naturally, Russia, its legal successor, which emerged on the ruins of the Soviet Union, did not want to lose its sphere of influence in the form of Georgia and began to use all methods against the new state that were available in the Soviet reserve. An unprecedented disinformation campaign was launched against Zviad Gamsakhurdia, according to which Zviad was accused of establishing authoritarianism, silencing critics, centralizing power, and so on. The reality was different: the head of state, who came to power, put all his efforts into conducting dialogue, seeking allies in the international arena, finding a common language with opposition parties, ensuring economic growth, eliminating internal conflicts, and protecting the rights of ethnic minorities.

Opposition political parties and groups, incited by Russia, accused Zviad Gamsakhurdia of acting against Georgia's interests. The accusations were so absurd that they could not be discussed. Therefore, it was decided to remove him by force. The confrontation in the Georgian capital turned into a civil war. Zviad Gamsakhurdia avoided being the cause of the confrontation between the sons of one nation because of him and first moved to Western Georgia to his supporters and then went abroad.

Zviad Gamsakhurdia was the first president of independent Georgia for a very short time: in 1991-1992. He did not actually manage to realize his foreign policy

¹³ Helsinki Decalogue (1 August 1975), https://www.cvce.eu/content/publication/2005/7/12/1bccd494-0f57-4816-ad18-6aaba4d73d56/publishable_en.pdf

¹⁴ The Geneva Conventions and their Commentaries, <https://www.icrc.org/en/law-and-policy/geneva-conventions-and-their-commentaries>

ideology. What were his political visions regarding Georgia's foreign policy? His period in office was short and turbulent, but several main approaches determined his foreign policy. These were:

1. Strong pro-Western orientation: Zviad Gamsakhurdia was a staunch defender of Georgia's independence. He linked Georgia's foreign policy to the West. He wanted to bring Georgia closer to European countries, because, as he emphasized in his speeches, there is no alternative to democratic values. Zviad Gamsakhurdia always emphasized Christian and European identity and considered Georgia historically a part of the European and Christian world. He welcomed Western observers during the elections and expressed openness to Western investments and cooperation.

2. Georgia's membership in international organizations: Zviad Gamsakhurdia sought Georgia's membership in the UN and the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe (CSCE).

3. The Russian Question: Zviad Gamsakhurdia viewed Russia as the main threat to Georgia's independence. He opposed Georgia's membership in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), believing it to be a way to reassert Moscow's dominance. His rhetoric was strongly anti-communist, portraying Georgia as a victim of Soviet imperialism. He refused to allow foreign military bases (including Russian) on Georgian territory. He openly accused Russia of sponsoring separatist movements in Abkhazia and the so-called South Ossetia, and of using ethnic conflict to divide Georgia.

4. Limited diplomatic infrastructure: Given the short duration of his presidency and Georgia's newly restored independence, the country lacked a well-developed foreign service. His government struggled to quickly establish effective diplomatic missions and strategic alliances abroad.

5. The United States: Zviad Gamsakhurdia often spoke of the United States as a model of democracy and a potential ally in Georgia's post-Soviet transition. He viewed the United States as the main counterweight to Russian influence in the region. Zviad hoped that Washington would more actively support the independence of Georgia and other former Soviet republics. After Georgia declared independence in April 1991, Gamsakhurdia's government turned to Washington for diplomatic recognition and economic assistance. Some early contacts were made with American diplomats, and Georgian representatives abroad worked to establish an embassy in Washington. The United States, it can be said, was displaying a certain geopolitical caution. In 1991, the United States still had relations with the disintegrated USSR. It preferred stability to quick recognition of the breakaway republics. Ultimately, the United States did not support its government. In early 1992, the government of the first president was overthrown. After the January 1992 military coup, the United States welcomed Eduard Shevardnadze, who had previously held the post of Foreign Minister of the Soviet Union, to Georgia and began active diplomatic relations with him.

The United States of America first became interested in the Georgian state during the referendum held

on March 31, 1991. President George W. Bush sent former US President Richard Nixon to the country on an unofficial visit. This visit confirmed the increased interest of the United States in the Georgian state and was considered a preparatory basis for new relations between the two states. At the same time, the visit also had a political connotation. By this fact, the US administration made Moscow feel that it respected the aspirations and decision of the Georgian population for the independence of the state.

During the visit of former President R. Nixon, details of a possible meeting between President Zviad Gamsakhurdia and the US President in the near future were also discussed. The first President of Georgia spoke about this several times during interviews, which indicates that he openly expressed a real desire for relations with America and the West. This fact is also confirmed by the fact that one of the Turkish guests paid attention to the American flags on the streets of Tbilisi. Zviad Gamsakhurdia told a Turkish journalist that negotiations were underway in these days about the meeting of the Georgian President with President George W. Bush in Washington. This is another clear example of the leaders of the national government declaring their clear readiness for relations with the United States.

The change in America's attitude towards Georgia was caused by the fact that on July 31, 1991, the United States reached another agreement on armaments with the USSR, this was the most important "Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty" with the Soviet Union, which George W. Bush and Mikhail Gorbachev signed in Moscow as a result of long negotiations. Naturally, in order to implement the treaty, the American president had to have good relations with the central government of the Soviet Union. George Bush would have officially stated his positive attitude towards the rebellious republics, of course, there would have been no point in thinking about implementing the agreement and all agreements would have collapsed. Therefore, the position of the President of the United States is understandable. In such a case, any positive or negative position of the Georgian government would have no meaning.

It is therefore wrong to accuse President Zviad Gamsakhurdia of attempting to isolate Georgia internationally. These processes were taking place independently, and no leader of such a small country could have stood up to the interests of a world power.

6. Limited Western support: Despite his efforts, Gamsakhurdia received limited tangible support from the West. When discussing President Zviad Gamsakhurdia's foreign policy, it is important to consider the fact that the Second Republic practically existed within the Soviet Union in 1990-1992, which explains the fact that Western leaders were unable to clearly state their position. According to the constitutional theory of international law, a newly emerged state only becomes a subject of international law when its independence and sovereignty are recognized by other states. In 1990-1991, Georgia was not admitted to any international organization. The desire of the national authorities of President Zviad Gamsakhurdia to

have friendly relations with the West and receive support from the leaders of various countries was not enough, moreover, the recognition of Georgia as an independent republic in the international arena was beyond the capabilities of the national authorities.

Conclusion

In the presented article, we tried to show an analysis of Georgia's foreign policy course and the most important stage of its formation in the first years of independence. We tried to show that Zviad Gamsakhurdia, as the President of Georgia, did everything for the international recognition of Georgia, but the political crisis and economic processes taking place in the world at that time, as well as the destructive actions of hostile forces in the country, did not allow him to work in a calm environment for the international recognition of the young Georgian state.

As a result of Zviad Gamsakhurdia's efforts, the Republic of Georgia has been a fully sovereign state since April 9, 1991, which is already a subject of international law and a member of a number of international organizations.

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